

Where did the time go

NuoFu Chen¹

¹School of New Energy, North China Electric Power University, Beijing 102206, China,

Email: nfchen@ncepu.edu.cn

The heliocentric theory has been widely accepted, which well explains the sunrise, sunset and the changes of four seasons. However, a strange phenomenon that cannot be explained by heliocentric theory has emerged. A point on Earth is at noon at the beginning. When the Earth rotates n circles and reaches the other side of the Sun, the clock time remains at noon at the same point, but according to the sunshine, it becomes midnight. Here we have improved the heliocentric model to avoid this strange phenomenon. If the direction of the Earth's axis rotates in the same period when the Earth revolves around the sun, the time on Earth will not be disordered. However, the consequence is that there will no longer be seasonal changes on Earth. A more reasonable model is that the Earth is stationary on one side of the Sun. While the Earth rotates around its axis, it rotates around the normal axis of the ecliptic plane, with a period of one year. Assuming that the Earth rotates, there will be an external repulsive force, which can counteract the sun's gravitational pull on the Earth. I hope that this model will become the starting point for a better model of the Earth's motion.

As long ago as 340 B.C. the Greek philosopher Aristotle thought that the earth was stationary and that the sun, the moon, the planets, and the stars moved in circular orbits around the earth.

This idea was elaborated by Ptolemy in the second century A.D. into a complete cosmological model. After more than a thousand year, a different model was proposed in 1514 by a Polish, Nicholas Copernicus¹. His idea was that the sun was stationary at the center, and that the earth and the other planets moved in circular orbits around the sun.

In heliocentric theory, the Earth undergoes three simultaneous movements¹: One is the rotation movement around the Earth's axis, once a day. It reasonably explains the alternation phenomenon of day and night on Earth. The second is the annual rotation around the sun. The third is that there is an angle of deviation between the Earth's axis and the normal axis of the ecliptic plane, and the Earth maintains the direction of its axis unchanged during its orbit around the sun. This explains the changes in the four seasons on Earth.

According to heliocentric theory, if the Earth starts rotating at position (a) with a period of T_1 , then after the Earth rotates n (n is an integer) circles, the positions of points A and B on the Earth should remain unchanged, as shown in Figure 1. When the Earth is in position (a), the time at point A and point B is midnight (0:00 or 24:00) and noon (12:00), respectively.

According to common sense, after the Earth rotates n circles, the time (clock time) at points A and B should remain unchanged. However, a strange phenomenon has emerged. Because $t=(t+nT_1)$, when the Earth rotates n circles and reaches the other side of the Sun, the clocks at points A and B should be the same as the Earth at position (a), at 0:00 and 12:00 respectively.

But according to the actual situation of sunshine, the time of point A and point B are 18:00 and 6:00, respectively. When the Earth orbits to position (c), the actual time of point A and point B is exactly opposite to that when the Earth is at position (a), with point A at noon and point B at midnight, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. When the Earth is at position (a), the time of points A and B is midnight and noon, respectively. After the Earth rotates for n cycles, the time at points A and B should remain unchanged. However, this is inconsistent with the actual sunshine situation at that time (b), (c), and (d).

In fact, if point B is at noon when the Earth is at position (a), point B is always at noon after the Earth has passed time of nT_1 . To solve the problem of inconsistency between the clock time and the actual time, we can make some improvements to the heliocentric model. Rotate the Earth's axis in the same period as the Earth's revolution. The clock time and actual time are agreed upon after the earth's axis rotates, as shown in Figure 2. However, a new problem has arisen, as if the Earth's axis were to rotate during its orbit, there would be no changes in the four seasons on Earth.

Figure 2. The clock time and actual time are agreed upon after the earth's axis rotate in the same period as the Earth's revolution.

There is a possibility that if the Earth is located on one side of the Sun without a revolution,

the Earth rotates around the its axis once a day and its axis around the normal axis of the ecliptic passing through the Earth's center once a year, then these problems can be solved, as shown in Figure 3. This model can explain the sunrise and sunset, as well as the changes in the four seasons of the year. There is also a problem with this model. If the Earth does not orbit the Sun, how does it resist the Sun's gravitational pull?

Figure 3. An improved Earth Rotation Model is that the Earth is located on one side of the Sun without a revolution, only the daily rotation around the Earth's axis and the annual rotation of the Earth's axis around the normal axis of the ecliptic passing through the Earth's center.

To solve the problem of the attraction from the sun, it is necessary to make another hypothesis that the Earth's rotation will generate repulsive forces on external objects. This external repulsive force F_r is proportional to its own mass, radius, and rotational speed, and is equivalent to the centrifugal force P_c generated by the Earth's rotation around the sun. F_r can be expressed as Equation 1, and P_c can be expressed as Equation 2 according to Newton's law.

$$F_r = \phi mr\omega^2 \quad (1)$$

$$F_c = \frac{mL4\pi^2}{T^2} \quad (2)$$

Where, ϕ is a dimensionless constant, m and r is the mass and the radius of the Earth, L is the

distance between the Earth and the Sun, T is the period of the Earth's rotation around the sun, and ω is the rotational angular velocity which can be expressed as Equation 3 illustrated by Figure 4.

Figure 4. The angular velocity of the Earth's rotation around its axis is ω_1 , and its normal component of the ecliptic is ω_{12} . The angular velocity of the Earth's axis rotating around the normal axis of the ecliptic is ω_2 . φ is the deviation angle between the Earth's axis and the normal axis of the ecliptic.

$$\omega = \omega_{12} + \omega_2 = \omega_1 \cos \varphi + \omega_2 = \frac{2\pi \cos \varphi}{T_1} + \frac{2\pi}{T_2} \quad (3)$$

Where ω_1 is the angular velocity of the Earth's rotation around its axis, and its normal component of the ecliptic is ω_{12} . The angular velocity of the Earth's axis rotating around the normal axis of the ecliptic is ω_2 . T_1 and T_2 are the periods correspond to angular velocities of ω_1 and ω_2 , respectively.

According to Equations 1 and 2, make F_r equal to F_c , it can be obtained that

$$\phi = \frac{L4\pi^2}{r\omega^2 T^2} = \frac{4\pi^2 L}{r \left(\frac{2\pi \cos \varphi}{T_1} + \frac{2\pi}{T_2} \right)^2 T^2} \quad (4)$$

The parameter value on the right side of Equation 4 is taken as $T_1=24$ hours= 8.64×10^4 s, $T=T_2=1$ year= 3.1536×10^7 s, $r=6371$ km, $L=1.496 \times 10^8$ km, $\varphi=23.5$ degrees. By substituting the data into Equation 4, it can be calculated that $\phi=0.2085$.

In summary, in the solar system:

- (1) Both the Sun and the Earth are fixed stars.
- (2) The sun has two satellites, Mercury and Venus.
- (3) The Earth has one satellite, the Moon.
- (4) Other planets rotate around the common center of mass between the Sun and Earth.
- (5) The Earth rotates from west to east around its axis, once a day.
- (6) There is a deviation angle φ between the Earth's axis and the normal axis of the ecliptic plane.
- (7) The Earth's axis rotates from west to east around the normal axis of the ecliptic passing through the Earth's center, once a year.

Although the above solar system model can reasonably explain sunrise, sunset, and seasonal changes, and also has solved the problem of inconsistency between clock time and actual reality, may not be the ultimate model. I hope it can become an initial model that attracts researcher's attention and further improvements. Finally, establish a model that conforms to the real solar system.

Reference

¹ Copernicus, N., Translated by Shihui Ye, *De Revolutionibus Orbium Coelestium*, Peking University Press, Beijing (2006).